

Evaluation of Aviation Management Programs in Turkish State Universities According to YÖK Atlas Data

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Aviation Aviation Management YÖK Atlas</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 27 March 2026 Revised: 7 June 2026 Accepted: 20 June 2026</p>	<p>This study aims to evaluate the Aviation Management programs of state universities in Türkiye based on the 2022, 2023, and 2024 YÖK Atlas data. Within the scope of this purpose, the data on Aviation Management programs at state universities were reviewed on the YÖK Atlas website, analyzed using the document analysis method, and the findings were reported. According to the findings of the study, Eskişehir Technical University ranked first in the three-year YKS placement ranking, followed by Kocaeli University and Erciyes University, while Iğdır University had the lowest YKS placement ranking. It can be said that Dicle University and İskenderun Technical University had the highest number of students placed in 2024. It can also be stated that the lowest general quota in 2022 was at Tarsus University and Malatya Turgut Özal University. It was concluded that the most preferred university in total in 2024 was Eskişehir Technical University, while the least preferred university was Iğdır University. Considering the geographical regions from which students were placed, a large proportion of the students placed at Dicle University were from the Southeastern Anatolia Region, where the university is located, while a large proportion of the students placed at Balıkesir University were from the Marmara Region, where the university is located. When the educational status of students placed over the three-year period is examined, it can be stated that, for all universities, the students were high school graduates and had not previously been placed in a university program. The gender distribution of students placed over the three-year period was 57% female and 43% male.</p>

1. Introduction

The aviation sector is constantly changing and developing in parallel with technological advancements. In order to keep pace with these developments and progress further, the sector requires a qualified, competent, knowledgeable, proactive, creative, and innovative workforce (Kanbur & Erol, 2017; Kanbur, Maziöğlu & Kanbur, 2023). Universities play a significant role in training this workforce and in equipping students with the knowledge and skills required by the sector. As the highest educational institutions in society, universities influence their regions socially, culturally, economically, and artistically. They also identify societal needs and contribute to the development of a qualified workforce in relevant fields. Therefore, their importance continues to increase (Üzülmez & Arslan, 2019; Kadirhanoğulları, 2023). In this context, it is important to analyze students enrolled in aviation management programs at universities, which are expected to respond to the needs of the developing

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and changing aviation sector. To present the findings obtained from such analyses, several studies have presented data on different programs and various parameters related to students admitted to universities through the university entrance examination (Aktaş, Ö. & Aktaş, 2018; Şimşek, Solmaz & Güleç, 2020; Durmuş & Tokyay, 2021; Yağcı & Güney, 2022). These studies have compared different programs and provided important data for stakeholders. Aviation is currently one of the most preferred sectors and attracts the interest of individuals from almost all age groups. This interest is particularly evident among young people who wish to pursue a career in aviation and who consider this field in their university preferences (Yavaş, 2021). Aviation is a rapidly developing, expanding, and highly demanded sector worldwide. It plays a significant role in the socio-economic development of societies and in improving their welfare levels (Türkay & Artar, 2021). The aviation sector differs from many other sectors due to the large number of regulations it involves, and all aviation-related activities are strictly governed by these regulations (Göv, 2018). In this sector, several factors come to the fore, including foreign language proficiency, adaptation to new technologies, sustainable performance, adherence to and compliance with regulations, quality systems, and an understanding of safety and security (Gerde, 2016). The aviation sector includes many complex structures and requires experienced, qualified, and competent employees to ensure the sustainability of these structures. Therefore, a higher education system aligned with international standards is needed to meet the demand for employees with these qualifications (Durali & Özdamar, 2021).

In Türkiye, civil aviation education began with the Civil Aviation Vocational School, which was established within Anadolu University in 1986, and the duration of education was extended to four years following a law enacted in 1992. In order to meet the increasing need for a qualified workforce in the aviation sector and to support developments in this field, the program was initially launched under the name “Civil Air Transport Management” and was later renamed “Aviation Management” (Yaçınkaya & Adiloğlu, 2012; Kiracı & Bayrak, 2014). Graduates of this program can work in ground services, airports, national and international airlines, catering and cargo companies, and other aviation-related institutions and organizations (Erdoğan, 2019; İnan, 2020). As of 2025, there are 20 Aviation Management programs continuing their education and training activities within state universities (YÖK Atlas, 2025).

2. Theoretical Background

The civil aviation sector has been one of the fastest-growing and most technologically advanced sectors in the world since the beginning of the 20th century. Due to the presence of many different systems, the aviation sector has a complex structure. In order to further develop and sustain this structure, it requires a workforce with sufficient technical knowledge, innovation, creativity, experience, and qualifications. To meet the aviation sector’s need for a workforce with this profile, educational institutions that meet international standards are required (Durali & Özdamar, 2021). In developing countries, the importance of educational institutions responsible for training qualified human resources that enable countries to compete with others in social, economic, technical, and political terms is increasing day by day (Delibaş & Babadoğan, 2009). Universities, especially those providing higher education, make significant contributions to employment, social structure, population, industrialization, socio-cultural structure, and urbanization in the cities and countries in which they are located (Sargın, 2007). Thus, universities, which undertake the mission of meeting the needs of the country and the era while responding to the increasing demand for higher education, have become very important educational institutions (Toprak, 2012). In Türkiye, the Higher Education Institutions Examination (YKS) is conducted by the Measurement, Selection and Placement Center (ÖSYM) to select and place students in undergraduate and associate degree programs according to their preferences. The YKS consists of three sessions: Session 1, the Basic Proficiency Test (BPT); Session 2, the Field Proficiency Tests (FPT); and Session 3, the Foreign Language Test (FLT) (Yağcı & Güzey, 2022).

In this context, studies that have utilized data from YÖK Atlas are summarized below. YÖK Atlas is a system developed by the Council of Higher Education (YÖK) that provides digital data on universities and their programs from previous years. It is continuously updated to help university candidates make more informed choices. Karaçam and Atmaca (2025) examined the changes observed in undergraduate programs of education faculties

in Türkiye between 2022 and 2024 using YÖK Atlas data. Their research revealed that the teaching profession has lost its appeal and that graduates perceive limited job opportunities. Ergün et al. (2023) stated in their study that a large proportion of the students who chose Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University were from Tokat province, that the proportion of male students was higher, that students' success rankings and minimum scores decreased over the years, that the majority graduated from Anatolian high schools, and that the first-choice preference rate for the Geography program increased over the years. Kadirhanogulları (2023) conducted a study to evaluate the number of students admitted to the biology teacher training program and their scores based on the 2020, 2021, and 2022 YÖK Atlas data. Şimşek, Solmaz, and Güleç (2020) evaluated the gastronomy and culinary arts departments of universities in the Aegean Region using YÖK Atlas data. Their study revealed that the number of students was higher, that students mostly came from the Aegean Region, and that they generally had general high school diplomas. In their study, Yağcı and Güney (2022) evaluated the private security and protection program based on the 2021 YÖK Atlas data. The study indicated that the students admitted to the program generally had low net averages and low success rates in quantitative subjects. Aktaş and Aktaş (2018) examined history departments and history teacher training programs using 2018 YÖK Atlas data. Their study indicated that the net averages of students admitted to history departments were generally low and that their achievement in quantitative subjects was close to zero.

3. Methodology

The aim of this research is to evaluate the Aviation Management programs of state universities in Türkiye based on the 2022, 2023, and 2024 YÖK Atlas data. The research population consists of 20 Aviation Management programs that continue their education and training activities within state universities as of 2025 (Table 1).

Table 1. State Universities with Aviation Management Programs (YÖK Atlas, 2025)

Eskişehir Technical University	Balıkesir University	Dicle University
Kocaeli University	Necmettin Erbakan University	Malatya Turgut Özal University
Erciyes University	Selçuk University	İskenderun Technical University
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	Tarsus University	Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University
Gaziantep University	Süleyman Demirel University	Gümüşhane University
Samsun University	Kastamonu University	Iğdır University
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University	Amasya University	

A scan pattern, one of the qualitative research techniques, was used to collect data from Aviation Management programs and to analyze these data comparatively. This scan pattern is a method that aims to describe a past or current situation as it exists (Karasar, 2012). Thus, the sources constituting the research data, such as documents and digital media, are reviewed, examined in depth, and analyzed to obtain enriched data (Yaprak, 2025). Using this method, students enrolled in public universities offering Aviation Management programs were systematically and statistically compared, and the findings obtained were evaluated. The evaluation and tabulation of the research data were carried out based on arithmetic means, frequencies, and the number of students admitted to the programs. The research data were collected from the YÖK Atlas database in July 2025 and tabulated for each category. The most significant limitation of the study is that the secondary data were obtained from the YÖK Atlas database.

4. Results and Discussion

A scan pattern was used in line with the aim of this study. YÖK Atlas data were used in the application of this model. The data were examined under seven main categories: Students' Placement Rankings (YKS Placement Rankings), Average Net Scores of Admitted Students in YKS, Nationwide Preference Statistics, Geographical Regions of Admitted Students, Educational Status of Admitted Students, Tendencies of Admitted Students to Prefer the Same or Different Programs, and Gender Distribution of Admitted Students.

Table 2. Student Placement Ranking (YKS Placement Ranking)

University	YKS Placement Ranking		
	2022	2023	2024
Eskişehir Technical University	165.715	138.867	109.033
Kocaeli University	244.039	218.419	163.493
Erciyes University	273.666	259.024	205.432
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	293.584	279.847	219.823
Gaziantep University	305.268	290.753	246.108
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University	347.179	313.315	249.520
Samsun University	401.591	355.475	252.283
Balıkesir University	366.499	332.117	252.605
Necmettin Erbakan University	371.851	364.618	270.542
Selçuk University	401.134	372.942	278.593
Tarsus University	470.996	394.456	281.914
Süleyman Demirel University	423.088	391.756	283.414
Amasya University	488.919	458.687	322.530
Kastamonu University	527.400	486.839	330.996
Malatya Turgut Özal University	490.000	459.059	332.390
Dicle University	550.685	471.133	392.395
İskenderun Technical University	456.933	586.739	418.889
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	728.921	655.130	449.187
Gümüşhane University	756.235	710.095	469.226
Iğdır University	1.206.983	1.123.971	775.698

Student Placement Ranking (YKS Placement Ranking): Over the past three years, Eskişehir Technical University ranked first in the YKS placement rankings, followed by Kocaeli University and Erciyes University, while Iğdır University had the lowest YKS placement ranking (Table 2). In YKS placements, it is expected that Eskişehir Technical University ranks first. This is because Eskişehir Technical University was established after separating from Anadolu University. Therefore, the university's Aviation Management program can be considered the oldest and most well-known program in Türkiye. In addition, the fact that Eskişehir Technical University offers master's and doctoral programs in this field helps the program become more widely known among students and positively affects the department's success ranking. On the other hand, the city's facilities, such as accommodation, entertainment, and transportation, its student-oriented character, and the expertise and experience of the program's academic staff also positively affect the university's success ranking. A similar situation can be said to apply to Kocaeli University, although it is newer than Eskişehir Technical University. The facilities of the city of Kocaeli, its location in the Marmara Region, the academic staff, and other opportunities significantly affect the university's success ranking. On the other hand, Iğdır University's lowest success ranking may be explained by factors such as its location in the far east of the country and the city's limited student-oriented facilities.

Average Net Scores of Admitted Students in the YKS Exam: Considering the average net scores over the three years, the lowest net scores in both TYT and AYT were observed in the TYT Science section (20 questions – 1.53 average). The highest net scores can be said to be in the TYT Turkish section (40 questions – 24.8 average) (Table 3). The Aviation Management program admits students based on the equal-weighted score type. Therefore, students admitted to this program are expected to have similar levels of numerical and verbal knowledge. However, when the data in the table are examined, it is seen that Turkish and social studies scores are higher, mathematics scores are relatively sufficient, but science scores are quite low. Based on the data in the table, it can be stated that students who choose the Aviation Management program have stronger verbal skills, whereas their numerical skills, especially in science, are weak.

Nationwide Preference Statistics: In 2022, 2023, and 2024, Eskişehir Technical University was the most preferred university overall, while Iğdır University was the least preferred (Table 4). Eskişehir Technical University

was established after separating from Anadolu University. Therefore, the university's Aviation Management program can be considered Türkiye's oldest and most well-known program. The city's amenities, such as accommodation, entertainment, and transportation, its student-oriented character, and the fact that the program's academic staff are experts and experienced in their field also positively influence the preference for the university. On the other hand, the low level of preference for Iğdır University can be attributed to factors such as the university's location in the far east of the country and the city's limited student-oriented facilities. Additionally, the fact that Iğdır University's Aviation Management program is offered within the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, rather than within a dedicated aviation-related faculty, may also be one of the reasons for its low level of preference.

Geographical Regions of Placement of Students: Considering the geographical regions from which students were placed, it can be said that the majority of students placed at Dicle University were from the Southeastern Anatolia Region, where the university is located, while the majority of students placed at Balıkesir University were from the Marmara Region, where the university is located. This finding generally shows that students tend to choose programs in the region where they live. There may be many reasons for this situation. In particular, financial difficulties, cultural differences, and family structure may be among these reasons. Considering the three-year period, it is seen that the highest number of students came from the Central Anatolia Region (778 students), while the lowest number came from the Eastern Anatolia Region (312 students) (Table 5).

Educational Background of Admitted Students: Looking at the educational background of admitted students over the three years, it can be concluded that, for all universities, the students were high school graduates and had not been admitted to a university before (Table 6). According to the findings in the table, almost all of the students placed in Aviation Management programs consisted of students who had either recently graduated from high school or retaken the university entrance exam after graduation, and they had not previously been placed in any higher education program.

Tendencies of Admitted Students to Choose the Same/Different Programs: Considering the data from the three-year period, it is observed that the preference tendency of admitted students is toward "Different Program Preferences" (Table 7). According to the findings, students placed in Aviation Management programs generally did not include this program among their first choices and instead preferred different programs. Therefore, it can be said that the fact that a large proportion of students did not choose the Aviation Management program as their first preference may negatively affect their academic success and career planning.

Gender Distribution of Students: According to the gender distribution of the total number of students admitted over the three-year period, 57% of the students were female (2,191 students), while 43% were male (1,621 students) (Table 8). According to the findings, it is observed that female students tend to prefer Aviation Management programs at universities. Studying Aviation Management, graduating from this program, and building a career in this field appear to attract female students more in terms of job requirements and working conditions. Especially when the 2024 data are examined, it can be said that there has been an increase in the number of female students. The sector's continuous job creation, attractiveness, and career opportunities may encourage more female students to choose this program.

Table 3. Average Net Scores of Admitted Students in the YKS Exam

University	Year	Average SSAS	Settled	BPT Turkish	BPT Social	BPT Math	BPT Science	FPT Math	FPT Turkish	FPT History	FPT Geography
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	425,997	62	27,1	13,1	18,0	4,2	13,3	14,0	4,2	4,6
	2023	429,021	62	28,0	13,7	18,2	3,6	14,4	15,2	4,8	3,4
	2024	442,527	62	29,5	13,2	18,8	2,8	11,0	16,8	5,9	3,5
Kocaeli University	2022	403,618	72	25,5	12,2	14,0	1,6	10,3	14,2	4,2	4,5
	2023	410,924	72	26,4	12,2	15,0	2,0	11,5	14,7	3,5	2,8
	2024	431,945	77	28,6	13,2	14,1	2,1	6,5	16,7	6,3	3,8
Erciyes University	2022	398,953	72	24,9	12,4	13,0	2,0	8,9	14,5	3,9	4,4
	2023	411,960	72	27,0	12,3	14,6	2,0	9,9	13,5	3,8	3,0
	2024	431,024	77	27,5	12,9	11,2	1,6	5,9	16,0	6,4	3,6

Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2022	403,401	72	25,5	12,4	11,6	2,3	7,1	13,8	3,9	4,4
	2023	410,666	72	27,2	12,6	13,8	1,7	8,8	13,5	3,9	2,5
	2024	434,696	72	26,8	12,7	12,0	1,4	5,2	16,0	5,8	3,7
Gaziantep University	2022	401,416	61	24,1	11,9	13,8	2,6	8,9	13,5	4,2	4,1
	2023	411,396	61	25,2	11,3	16,7	1,4	12,5	10,8	3,6	2,1
	2024	413,827	65	27,2	12,5	12,5	1,6	5,9	14,8	5,9	3,2
Samsun University	2022	388,324	72	24,2	11,5	9,4	1,9	5,2	13,5	3,9	4,3
	2023	412,307	72	26,3	12,0	10,7	1,1	7,4	13,4	3,6	2,7
	2024	413,970	72	28,0	12,3	10,9	1,6	4,6	15,5	5,8	3,6
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat Uni.	2022	398,207	62	24,9	12,0	10,6	1,7	6,0	12,9	4,2	4,3
	2023	400,874	62	26,4	11,8	12,4	1,3	7,8	13,3	3,8	2,8
	2024	416,521	67	27,7	12,1	10,8	1,7	4,6	15,1	6,1	3,6
Balıkesir University	2022	401,460	62	24,6	11,3	11,1	1,9	6,4	12,5	3,9	4,1
	2023	407,784	62	26,0	11,8	10,9	0,9	7,0	14,0	2,9	2,9
	2024	416,844	62	27,2	12,9	10,7	1,3	4,5	15,5	5,6	3,5
Necmettin Erbakan University	2022	401,895	72	23,8	11,7	10,9	2,2	6,2	12,7	3,9	4,4
	2023	406,731	72	25,6	11,7	10,8	1,3	6,8	13,2	3,4	2,7
	2024	422,675	77	26,9	12,1	10,7	2,0	4,2	15,0	5,5	3,5
Selçuk University	2022	397,269	72	24,3	10,7	9,6	1,6	6,0	12,4	3,8	4,1
	2023	402,661	72	25,0	11,5	10,8	1,0	6,8	13,2	3,2	2,7
	2024	419,749	77	26,0	12,2	9,9	1,5	4,3	15,3	5,8	3,4
İskenderun Technical University	2022	387,369	72	23,2	10,7	9,2	1,3	4,7	12,8	3,6	3,9
	2023	388,990	72	23,4	10,9	7,9	0,9	4,6	11,3	3,0	2,3
	2024	398,381	75	25,2	11,9	6,1	1,3	2,9	13,6	5,0	3,4
Tarsus University	2022	389,884	31	23,9	11,4	8,3	1,8	3,1	11,4	4,1	3,9
	2023	399,352	31	25,0	11,9	9,4	0,9	5,8	13,1	3,5	2,4
	2024	408,536	36	27,6	12,4	10,3	1,1	3,8	14,6	5,8	3,3
Süleyman Demirel University	2022	397,718	41	24,5	10,5	8,9	2,1	5,0	12,2	3,4	4,2
	2023	405,038	41	25,4	11,6	12,1	0,9	7,1	12,4	2,7	2,4
	2024	423,478	47	26,8	12,6	10,0	1,4	4,1	14,3	5,4	3,5
Kastamonu University	2022	384,245	62	23,1	10,4	6,9	1,5	3,1	11,7	3,4	4,2
	2023	396,509	62	23,6	11,2	8,8	1,1	5,4	12,3	3,0	2,3
	2024	404,898	67	25,6	12,2	8,6	1,3	3,4	14,3	5,6	3,6
Amasya University	2022	397,757	52	22,2	9,7	8,7	1,7	4,6	10,8	3,4	3,8
	2023	393,940	52	24,8	10,9	8,0	0,4	4,2	13,7	3,0	2,7
	2024	415,995	57	25,0	12,0	8,0	1,1	3,3	14,2	5,7	3,7
Dicle University	2022	386,555	72	23,6	10,1	11,3	2,1	5,2	10,7	3,8	4,3
	2023	396,890	72	24,3	11,8	10,5	1,0	7,1	10,7	4,2	2,5
	2024	400,753	75	24,8	11,8	8,4	1,0	3,7	13,4	5,3	3,6
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2022	382,297	31	21,6	10,6	8,1	2,1	3,9	12,4	3,8	4,2
	2023	398,731	39	25,0	12,4	10,1	1,0	6,0	12,1	3,3	2,6
	2024	407,720	45	26,4	11,7	7,4	0,9	3,2	14,7	5,4	3,4
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2022	375,948	62	19,8	9,7	5,8	1,3	3,1	9,9	3,4	3,7
	2023	392,438	62	23,4	10,3	6,3	1,3	4,0	9,8	2,5	2,2
	2024	403,046	62	24,8	11,4	7,6	0,5	2,9	12,3	5,4	3,3
Gümüşhane University	2022	393,813	41	19,2	8,5	5,5	1,0	3,3	9,6	2,9	3,2
	2023	376,172	41	21,5	9,6	6,7	0,7	4,0	10,3	2,2	2,2
	2024	396,932	47	23,8	10,6	6,1	0,9	2,8	12,6	4,5	3,3
İğdir University	2022	365,489	62	15,2	6,8	3,0	1,0	1,4	6,9	2,3	3,6
	2023	374,129	62	17,3	8,0	4,2	0,7	2,6	6,3	1,6	1,4
	2024	387,301	62	20,5	8,8	4,9	1,4	1,8	9,3	3,8	2,9

Table 4. Nationwide Preference Statistics

University	Year	Total number of candidates who chose this option	Average Rank of Preference	Number of those who chose it as their first preference	Number of people who chose it as one of their top 3 preferences	Number of those who chose it among the top 9 options	Number of those who prefer 10 or more options
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	2.216	7,1	552-%24,9	886-%40,0	1603-%72,3	613-%27,7
	2023	1.800	6,6	477-%26,5	779-%43,3	1293-%71,8	507-%28,2
	2024	3.565	6,0	1102-%30,9	1749-%49,1	2732-%76,6	833-%23,4
Kocaeli University	2022	1.608	7,6	197-%12,3	569-%35,4	1110-%69,0	498-%30,9
	2023	1.397	8,0	141-%10,1	442-%31,6	928-%66,4	469-%33,6
	2024	2.749	7,0	311-%11,3	1053-%38,3	2003-%72,9	746-%27,1
Erciyes University	2022	1.711	7,6	231-%13,5	582-%34,0	1195-%69,8	516-%30,2
	2023	1.222	7,3	192-%15,7	433-%35,4	863-%70,6	359-%29,4
	2024	2.300	6,9	326-%14,2	895-%38,9	1691-%73,5	609-%26,5
	2022	1.704	8,7	148-%8,7	452-%26,5	1076-%63,1	628-%36,9

Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2023	1.391	8,1	128-%9,2	419-%30,1	911-%65,5	480-%34,5
	2024	2.680	7,6	285-%10,6	821-%30,6	1851-%69,1	829-%30,9
Gaziantep University	2022	1.073	7,0	221-%20,6	438-%40,8	786-%73,3	287-%16,9
	2023	1.071	6,4	254-%23,7	481-%44,9	818-%76,4	253-%23,6
	2024	1.192	6,7	263-%22,1	478-%40,1	895-%75,1	297-%24,9
Samsun University	2022	1.949	8,8	157-%8,1	457-%23,4	1216-%62,4	733-%37,6
	2023	1.471	7,6	164-%11,1	409-%27,8	1019-%69,3	452-%30,7
	2024	2.670	7,6	305-%11,4	762-%28,5	1877-%70,3	793-%29,7
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat Uni.	2022	1.814	8,5	173-%9,5	460-%25,4	1178-%64,9	636-%35,1
	2023	1.213	8,1	105-%8,7	318-%26,2	816-%67,3	397-%32,7
	2024	2.512	7,5	244-%9,7	773-%30,8	1764-%70,2	748-%29,8
Balıkesir University	2022	1.805	8,8	125-%6,9	390-%21,6	1102-%61,1	703-%38,9
	2023	1.395	8,1	117-%8,4	377-%27,0	916-%65,7	479-%34,3
	2024	2.680	7,6	185-%6,9	683-%25,5	1901-%70,9	779-%29,1
Necmettin Erbakan University	2022	1.304	8,5	88-%6,7	294-%22,5	828-%63,5	476-%36,5
	2023	1.074	7,6	102-%9,5	307-%28,6	737-%68,6	337-%31,4
	2024	2.108	7,7	132-%6,3	532-%25,2	1464-%69,4	644-%30,5
Selçuk University	2022	1.926	8,7	118-%6,1	402-%20,9	1189-%61,7	737-%38,2
	2023	1336	7,6	115-%8,6	364-%27,2	941-%70,4	395-%29,5
	2024	2.465	7,8	158-%6,4	621-%25,2	1683-%68,3	782-%31,7
İskenderun Technical University	2022	1.226	8,9	109-%8,9	280-%22,8	761-%62,1	465-%37,9
	2023	625	8,2	80-%12,8	187-%29,9	406-%65,0	219-%35,04
	2024	1.301	8,0	164-%12,6	384-%29,5	853-%65,6	448-%34,4
Tarsus University	2022	1.448	9,0	144-%9,9	386-%26,7	891-%61,5	557-%38,4
	2023	947	8,8	56-%5,9	177-%18,7	590-%62,3	357-%37,7
	2024	1.754	8,4	105-%6,0	371-%21,2	1143-%65,2	611-%34,8
Süleyman Demirel University	2022	1.205	9,5	72-%6,0	216-%17,9	694-%57,6	511-%42,4
	2023	962	8,5	69-%7,2	194-%20,2	611-%63,5	351-%36,4
	2024	1.583	8,4	90-%5,7	310-%19,6	1045-%66,0	538-%34
Kastamonu University	2022	1.585	10,1	114-%7,2	325-%20,5	860-%54,3	725-%45,7
	2023	1.032	8,4	83-%8,0	240-%23,3	659-%63,9	373-%36,1
	2024	1.877	8,5	126-%6,7	405-%21,6	1196-%63,7	681-%36,2
Amasya University	2022	1.385	10,1	91-%6,6	250-%18,1	553-%39,746	639-%46,1
	2023	842	8,9	52-%6,2	170-%20,2	511-%60,7	331-%39,3
	2024	1.741	8,7	121-%7,0	357-%20,5	1078-%61,9	663-%38,1
Dicle University	2022	1.119	8,2	164-%14,7	360-%32,2	745-%66,6	374-%33,4
	2023	1215	7,8	176-%14,5	393-%32,3	810-%66,7	405-%33,3
	2024	957	7,8	147-%15,4	317-%33,1	646-%67,5	311-%32,5
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2022	1.117	9,9	77-%6,9	204-%18,3	620-%55,5	497-%44,5
	2023	644	9,4	42-%6,5	114-%17,7	383-%59,5	261-%40,5
	2024	967	8,9	60-%6,2	192-%19,9	587-%60,7	380-%39,3
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2022	651	9,3	45-%6,9	163-%25,0	559-%390	261-%40,1
	2023	700	8,6	56-%8,0	169-%24,1	432-%61,7	268-%38,3
	2024	1.118	8,9	103-%9,2	285-%25,5	679-%60,7	439-%39,3
Gümüşhane University	2022	442	11,0	19-%4,3	62-%14,0	214-%48,4	228-%51,6
	2023	593	9,8	28-%4,7	109-%18,4	335-%56,5	258-%43,5
	2024	1.102	9,3	76-%6,9	251-%22,8	641-%58,2	461-%41,8
İğdır University	2022	263	10,4	7-%2,7	37-%14,1	141-%53,6	122-%46,4
	2023	576	10,5	56-%9,7	119-%20,7	302-%52,4	274-%47,6
	2024	699	9,4	79-%11,3	163-%23,3	400-%57,2	299-%42,8

Table 5: Geographic Regions of Settlers (Total Number of Settlers)

University	Year	Settled	Marmara	Aegean	Mediterranean	Central Anatolia	Blacksea	Eastern Anatolia	Southeastern Anatolia
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	62	13	16	11	13	6	3	-
	2023	62	17	8	10	15	9	2	1
	2024	62	20	13	8	17	1	1	2
Kocaeli University	2022	72	27	8	10	13	9	2	3
	2023	72	25	8	9	19	6	3	2
	2024	77	29	9	11	16	9	3	-
Erciyes University	2022	72	1	4	6	47	2	7	5
	2023	72	3	4	15	40	7	-	3
	2024	77	3	6	11	39	16	2	-
	2022	72	21	19	13	13	3	1	2

Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2023	72	22	25	14	5	4	1	1
	2024	72	13	24	10	10	3	4	8
Gaziantep University	2022	62	4	-	9	3	1	2	43
	2023	77	-	-	12	3	2	2	58
Samsun University	2024	83	2	2	16	3	1	3	56
	2022	72	5	6	5	8	40	4	4
	2023	72	8	2	4	9	42	5	2
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat Uni.	2024	72	5	2	3	17	40	3	2
	2022	62	9	13	16	8	6	6	4
	2023	62	13	10	18	6	6	4	5
Balıkesir University	2024	67	7	17	18	10	10	2	3
	2022	62	26	10	9	7	4	3	3
	2023	62	30	13	2	7	7	2	1
Necmettin Erbakan University	2024	62	29	8	5	11	5	2	2
	2022	72	5	11	8	35	5	2	6
	2023	72	8	6	10	36	6	1	5
Selçuk University	2024	77	5	8	15	39	5	2	3
	2022	72	8	6	11	32	3	4	8
	2023	72	4	10	17	26	4	5	6
İskenderun Technical University	2024	77	6	10	12	33	13	1	2
	2022	72	3	4	41	9	-	-	15
	2023	90	3	1	42	8	1	6	29
Tarsus University	2024	96	6	7	39	15	4	5	20
	2022	31	3	2	10	5	1	2	8
	2023	31	3	-	16	4	1	3	4
Süleyman Demirel University	2024	36	1	1	17	5	3	1	8
	2022	41	9	10	12	7	1	-	2
	2023	41	4	10	16	5	2	1	3
Kastamonu University	2024	47	7	10	19	6	-	2	3
	2022	62	16	7	7	14	15	2	1
	2023	62	6	2	4	19	24	1	6
Amasya University	2024	67	14	3	6	13	24	3	4
	2022	52	6	4	6	16	12	3	5
	2023	52	8	1	7	17	13	1	5
Dicle University	2024	57	5	6	11	12	17	3	3
	2022	72	4	2	2	-	-	4	60
	2023	90	-	-	2	-	-	5	83
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2024	96	4	5	11	3	-	12	61
	2022	31	2	-	1	4	-	14	10
	2023	39	5	-	9	2	-	16	7
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2024	45	2	2	13	1	2	18	7
	2022	62	4	3	3	10	7	28	7
	2023	62	4	-	12	5	9	24	8
Gümüşhane University	2024	62	3	1	4	12	19	19	4
	2022	41	6	1	8	6	11	1	8
	2023	41	5	3	4	12	9	3	5
İğdir University	2024	47	3	3	8	11	9	7	6
	2022	62	4	6	6	7	1	18	20
	2023	62	3	1	11	4	6	16	21
TOTAL	2024	62	6	2	10	6	2	12	24
TOTAL		3812	517	375	675	778	468	312	687

Table 6: Educational Background of Admitted Students (Total Number of Admitted Students)

Üniversite	Year	Settled	A recent high school graduate taking the YKS exam for the first time.	High school graduate, never previously enrolled in university	While a student at university, he/she took the exam and was accepted here.	Previously graduated from a university	Other
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	62	32	28	2	-	-
	2023	62	25	34	2	1	-
	2024	62	41	20	1	-	-
Kocaeli University	2022	72	21	48	2	-	1
	2023	72	24	44	1	2	1
	2024	77	48	27	1	1	-
Erciyes University	2022	72	22	44	2	3	1

	2023	72	23	47	1	1	-
	2024	77	31	45	1	-	-
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2022	72	29	41	-	1	1
	2023	72	32	38	1	-	1
	2024	72	39	30	2	1	-
Gaziantep University	2022	62	15	35	3	9	-
	2023	77	10	43	6	18	-
	2024	83	31	42	4	4	2
Samsun University	2022	72	19	46	2	2	3
	2023	72	22	45	1	2	2
	2024	72	23	46	2	1	-
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat Uni.	2022	62	24	35	1	1	1
	2023	62	22	35	1	2	2
	2024	67	30	37	-	-	-
Balıkesir University	2022	62	21	37	1	2	1
	2023	62	25	36	1	-	-
	2024	62	40	20	1	1	-
Necmettin Erbakan University	2022	72	24	43	1	3	1
	2023	72	21	45	2	4	-
	2024	77	35	38	4	-	-
Selçuk University	2022	72	28	40	1	2	1
	2023	72	24	46	-	1	1
	2024	77	41	34	1	1	-
İskenderun Technical University	2022	72	21	44	1	5	1
	2023	90	22	55	4	9	-
	2024	96	36	56	3	1	-
Tarsus University	2022	31	12	16	-	3	-
	2023	31	4	22	1	4	-
	2024	36	13	21	1	1	-
Süleyman Demirel University	2022	41	21	18	2	-	-
	2023	41	14	26	-	1	-
	2024	47	22	22	2	-	1
Kastamonu University	2022	62	21	38	-	3	-
	2023	62	14	43	-	3	2
	2024	67	22	42	1	2	-
Amasya University	2022	52	21	26	-	4	1
	2023	52	24	26	2	-	-
	2024	57	26	30	1	-	-
Dicle University	2022	72	6	28	13	24	1
	2023	90	7	36	11	26	1
	2024	96	17	66	4	9	-
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2022	31	6	21	3	1	-
	2023	39	7	26	2	2	2
	2024	45	17	26	-	1	1
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2022	62	19	31	4	6	2
	2023	62	17	36	2	4	3
	2024	62	31	29	1	-	1
Gümüşhane University	2022	41	11	28	2	-	-
	2023	41	14	26	-	1	-
	2024	47	15	31	-	1	-
Iğdır University	2022	62	16	35	2	6	3
	2023	62	16	32	4	10	-
	2024	62	23	28	4	6	1

Table 7: Tendencies of Admitted Students to Choose the Same/Different Programs (Number of Admitted Students Based on General Quota)

University	Year	Settled	"Aviation Management (Faculty)" Preferences	"Different Program" Preference	"Associate Degree" Preferences	"Cyprus" Preferences	"Foreign" Preferences
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	62	141	609	26	-	-
	2023	62	108	538	16	-	-
	2024	62	125	537	7	9	-
Kocaeli University	2022	72	158	827	34	-	-
	2023	72	175	728	50	-	-
	2024	77	244	493	34	-	-

Erciyes University	2022	72	170	693	79	-	-
	2023	72	169	602	80	2	-
	2024	77	229	561	71	-	-
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2022	72	148	807	72	1	-
	2023	72	124	691	65	1	-
	2024	72	157	748	38	4	-
Gaziantep University	2022	62	125	473	50	2	-
	2023	77	94	434	60	3	-
	2024	83	181	419	87	-	-
Samsun University	2022	72	162	665	127	-	-
	2023	72	151	526	79	1	-
	2024	72	158	518	54	-	-
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat Uni.	2022	62	187	759	56	6	-
	2023	62	179	649	46	9	-
	2024	67	195	538	175	13	-
Balıkesir University	2022	62	142	764	83	-	-
	2023	62	149	546	74	1	-
	2024	62	145	657	59	-	-
Necmettin Erbakan University	2022	72	239	734	114	1	-
	2023	72	194	573	108	5	-
	2024	77	274	593	109	3	-
Selçuk University	2022	72	168	671	175	-	-
	2023	72	165	610	126	-	-
	2024	77	192	639	94	-	-
İskenderun Technical University	2022	72	214	530	86	5	-
	2023	72	285	645	144	-	-
	2024	75	287	484	249	8	-
Tarsus University	2022	31	109	306	71	-	-
	2023	31	78	328	49	10	-
	2024	36	117	229	61	-	-
Süleyman Demirel University	2022	41	113	397	66	-	-
	2023	41	114	331	66	11	-
	2024	47	120	358	13	-	-
Kastamonu University	2022	62	168	650	144	-	-
	2023	62	207	454	164	2	-
	2024	67	223	461	132	7	-
Amasya University	2022	52	151	626	76	-	-
	2023	52	181	496	146	-	1
	2024	57	227	422	105	10	-
Dicle University	2022	72	122	432	153	-	-
	2023	72	91	362	157	-	-
	2024	75	262	557	169	2	-
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2022	31	81	272	85	3	-
	2023	39	84	367	27	6	-
	2024	45	129	278	62	-	-
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2022	62	214	626	197	2	-
	2023	62	196	440	223	17	-
	2024	62	249	432	171	-	-
Gümüşhane University	2022	41	187	40	118	4	-
	2023	41	156	368	194	3	-
	2024	47	223	378	128	-	-
İğdir University	2022	62	180	656	373	7	-
	2023	62	126	652	359	11	-
	2024	62	200	493	248	2	1

Table 8: Gender Distribution of Students (Total Students)

University	Year	Settled	Female	Male
Eskişehir Technical University	2022	62	31	31
	2023	62	38	24
	2024	62	33	29
Kocaeli University	2022	72	28	44
	2023	72	43	29
	2024	77	46	31
Erciyes University	2022	72	36	36
	2023	72	39	33

	2024	77	58	19
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	2022	72	30	42
	2023	72	41	31
	2024	72	55	17
Gaziantep University	2022	62	33	29
	2023	77	38	39
	2024	83	52	31
Samsun University	2022	72	41	31
	2023	72	41	31
	2024	72	50	22
Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University	2022	62	31	31
	2023	62	30	32
	2024	67	44	23
Balıkesir University	2022	62	38	24
	2023	62	33	29
	2024	62	50	12
Necmettin Erbakan University	2022	72	27	45
	2023	72	43	29
	2024	77	48	29
Selçuk University	2022	72	29	43
	2023	72	35	37
	2024	77	55	22
İskenderun Technical University	2022	72	43	29
	2023	90	50	40
	2024	96	58	38
Tarsus University	2022	31	15	16
	2023	31	19	12
	2024	36	22	14
Süleyman Demirel University	2022	41	17	24
	2023	41	22	19
	2024	47	34	13
Kastamonu University	2022	62	38	24
	2023	62	40	22
	2024	67	45	22
Amasya University	2022	52	29	23
	2023	52	32	20
	2024	57	41	16
Dicle University	2022	72	33	39
	2023	90	46	44
	2024	96	63	33
Malatya Turgut Özal University	2022	31	15	16
	2023	39	26	13
	2024	45	32	13
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University	2022	62	27	35
	2023	62	40	22
	2024	62	39	23
Gümüşhane University	2022	41	22	19
	2023	41	26	15
	2024	47	33	14
İğdır University	2022	62	19	43
	2023	62	32	30
	2024	62	37	25
TOTAL		3812	2191	1621

5. Conclusion

The Aviation Management program is a crucial program that trains the qualified workforce needed by the aviation sector and helps address the employment shortage in this field. Through both theoretical and practical training, it contributes to the sector by enabling individuals to gain professional competencies. Examining the past and

present situations of students enrolled in Aviation Management programs, which train employees essential to the sector, and taking appropriate measures are important. In this context, the aim of this study is to evaluate the Aviation Management programs of 20 state universities in Türkiye based on the 2022, 2023, and 2024 YÖK Atlas data. For this purpose, a scan pattern, a qualitative research method, was used. The findings were evaluated and interpreted. Considering the average YKS net scores of students admitted in 2022, 2023, and 2024, it can be concluded that the lowest net scores were in TYT Science (20 questions – 1.53), while the highest net scores were in TYT Turkish (40 questions – 24.8). Given that Aviation Management programs admit students based on the equal-weighted (EA) score type, it is expected that Turkish language scores will be high and Science scores will be low.

In the nationwide preference statistics for the same years, Eskişehir Technical University was the most preferred university overall, while Iğdır University was the least preferred. The fact that Eskişehir Technical University's Aviation Management program was the first to be established significantly contributes to its high level of preference. Similarly, it is not surprising that Iğdır University, which is geographically located in the far east of the country, was the least preferred. On the other hand, it was found that a large proportion of the students admitted to Dicle University were from the Southeastern Anatolia Region, where the university is located, while a large proportion of the students admitted to Balıkesir University were from the Marmara Region, where the university is located. There may be many reasons why universities are preferred more by students from their own regions. Economic, cultural, and social factors can be listed among these reasons.

Looking at the educational backgrounds of students admitted in 2022, 2023, and 2024, it can be stated that, for all universities, the vast majority of students were high school graduates who had not previously been admitted to a university program. It can also be concluded that some students took a break after high school and/or had previously taken the university entrance exam but were either not placed in their preferred program or made different choices. Similarly, considering the data from the three-year period, it is seen that the preference trends of the admitted students were toward "Different Program Preferences." Although Aviation Management programs were among their preferences, it is clearly seen that preferences for different programs were more dominant. Finally, according to the gender distribution of the total number of students admitted in 2022, 2023, and 2024, the data indicated that 57% of the students were female (2,191 students), while 43% were male (1,621 students). Therefore, it can be concluded that the Aviation Management program was preferred more by female students.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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